

Supplementary Materials: Amphiphilic Triazine-Phosphorus Metallodendrons Possessing Anti-Cancer Stem Cell Activity

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S1. NMR Spectra

^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3).

$^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃).

³¹P{¹H} NMR (162 MHz, CDCl₃).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆).

¹³C{¹H} NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-d₆).

$^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR (162 MHz, DMSO- d_6).

Figure S2. DLS profiles of CuD and AuD metallodendrons stored for >9 months as a DMSO solution and diluted to 50 μ M before measurement (left). DLS profiles of CuD and AuD metallodendrons stored for >9 months as 50 μ M solution in water (right).

Figure S3. Zeta potential profiles of 50 μ M water solutions of CuD (top) and AuD (bottom) metallodendrons.